

ON SOME CONVERGENT SERIES

by Emil Burton

Notations :

N^* set of integers 1, 2, 3, ...

$d(n)$ the number of divisors of n .

$S(n)$ the Smarandache function $S : N^* \rightarrow N^*$.

$\hat{S}(n)$ is the smallest integer m with the property that $m!$ is divisible by n

R set of real numbers.

In this article we consider the series $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} f(S(k))$.

$f : N^* \rightarrow R$ is a function which satisfies any conditions.

Proposition 1. Let $f : N \rightarrow R$ be a function which satisfies condition :

$$f(t) \leq \frac{c}{t^{\alpha}(d(t!) - d((t-1)!))}$$

for every $t \in N^*$, $\alpha > 1$ constant, $c > 0$ constant.

Then the series $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} f(S(k))$ is convergent.

Proof: Let us denote by m_t the number of elements of the set

$$M_t = \{k \in N^* ; S(k) = t\} = \{k \in N^* ; k | t! \text{ and } k \nmid (t-1)!\}.$$

It follows that $m_t = d(t!) - d((t-1)!)$.

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} f(S(k)) = \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} m_t f(t)$$

We have $m_t \cdot f(t) \leq m_t \cdot \frac{c}{t^{\alpha} m_t} = \frac{c}{t^{\alpha}}$.

It is well - known that $\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{t^{\alpha}}$ is convergent if $\alpha > 1$.

Therefore $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} f(S(k)) < \infty$.

It is known that $d(n) < 2\sqrt{n}$ if $n \in N^*$ (2)

and it is obvious that $m_t < d(t!)$ (3)

We can show that

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (S(k)^p \sqrt{S(k)!})^{-1} < \infty, \quad p > 1 \tag{4}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (S(k)!)^{-1} < \infty \tag{5}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (S(1)! S(2)! \dots S(k)!)^{-1/k} < \infty \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} (S(k) \sqrt{S(k)!} (\log S(k))^p)^{-1} < \infty, \quad p > 1 \quad (7)$$

Write $f(S(k)) = (S(k)^p \cdot \sqrt{S(k)!})^{-1}$, $f(t) = (t^p \cdot \sqrt{t!})^{-1} = 2(t^p \cdot \sqrt{t!})^{-1} < 2(t^p \cdot d(t!))^{-1} < 2(t^p \cdot (d(t!) - d((t-1)!)))^{-1}$.

Now use the proposition 1 to get (4).

The convergence of (5) follows from inequality $t\sqrt{t!} < t!$ if $p \in \mathbb{R}$, $p > 1$, $t > t_0 = \lceil e^{2p+1} \rceil$, $t \in \mathbb{N}^*$. Here $\lceil e^{2p+1} \rceil$ means the greatest integer $\leq e^{2p+1}$.

The details are left to the reader. To show (6) we can use the Carleman's Inequality: Let $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}^*}$ be a sequence of positive real numbers and $x_n \neq 0$ for some n . Then

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (x_1 x_2 \dots x_k)^{1/k} < e \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} x_k \quad (8)$$

Write $x_k = (S(k)!)^{-1}$ and use (8) and (5) to get (6).

It is well-known that

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (n(\log n)^p)^{-1} < \infty \quad \text{if and only if } p > 1, \quad p \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (9)$$

Write $f(t) = (t\sqrt{t!} (\log t)^p)^{-1}$, $t \geq 2$, $t \in \mathbb{N}^*$. We have

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} (S(k) \sqrt{S(k)!} (\log S(k))^p)^{-1} = \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} m_k f(t).$$

$$m_k f(t) < d(t!) f(t) < 2 \sqrt{t!} (t \sqrt{t!} (\log t)^p)^{-1} = 2 (t (\log t)^p)^{-1}.$$

Now use (9) to get (7).

Remark 1. Apply (5) and Cauchy's Condensation Test to see that

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} 2^k (S(2^k)!)^{-1} < \infty. \quad \text{This implies that } \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} 2^k (S(2^k)!)^{-1} = 0.$$

A problem: Test the convergence behaviour of the series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (S(n)^p \sqrt{(S(n)-1)!})^{-1}. \quad (10)$$

Remark 2. This problem is more powerful than (4).

Let p_n denote the n -th prime number ($p_1=2$, $p_2=3$, $p_3=5$, $p_4=7$, ...).

$$\text{It is known that } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 1/p_n = \infty. \quad (11)$$

We next make use of (11) to obtain the following result:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} S(n)/n^2 = \infty. \quad (12)$$

$$\text{We have } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} S(n)/n^2 \geq \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} S(p_k)/p_k^2 = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} p_k/p_k^2 = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 1/p_k \quad (13)$$

Now apply (13) and (11) to get (12).

We can also show that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} S(n)/n^{1+p} < \infty \text{ if } p > 1, p \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Indeed, } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} S(n)/n^{1+p} \leq \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n/n^{1+p} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 1/n^p < \infty.$$

If $0 \leq p \leq 2$, we have $S(n)/n^p \geq S(n)/n^2$.

$$\text{Therefore } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} S(n)/n^p = \infty \text{ if } 0 \leq p \leq 2.$$

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